

APPLICATION OF NEW PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES IN EDUCATIONAL PROCESS

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Abstract. Today, many pedagogical technologies are used when teaching English. It is designed to make complex topics more understandable and memorable for students. The article provides for the use of new modern pedagogical technologies, the application of “heuristic education” technology to the English language, which will increase the activity, motivation, involvement of students and improve the quality of the lesson.

Key words: pedagogical technology, heuristic educational technology, task, handouts, heuristic didactics.

ПРИМЕНЕНИЕ НОВЫХ ПЕДАГОГИЧЕСКИХ ТЕХНОЛОГИЙ В ОБРАЗОВАТЕЛЬНОМ ПРОЦЕССЕ

Аннотация. Сегодня при обучении английскому языку используется множество педагогических технологий. Он призван сделать сложные темы более понятными и запоминающимися для учащихся. В статье предусмотрено использование новых современных педагогических технологий, применение технологии «эвристического обучения» к английскому языку, что позволит повысить активность, мотивацию, вовлеченность учащихся и улучшить качество урока.

Ключевые слова: педагогическая технология, эвристическая образовательная технология, задание, раздаточный материал, эвристическая дидактика.

Instructional technology is an innovative approach to teaching technical subjects that is highly effective for students. It uses technology tools to create a more engaging and interactive learning experience.

Instructional technology can be used effectively in engineering education, including video lectures, simulations, animations, and virtual laboratories to help students visualize complex concepts and gain hands-on skills. This allows students to learn at their own pace and according to their individual learning style, which improves understanding and retention of material.

In addition, educational technologies provide rapid feedback and diagnostic tools that allow students to identify their strengths and weaknesses. Teachers can also monitor their progress and provide personalized support and feedback based on their needs. This approach can lead to increased motivation and overall performance, which can have a positive impact on learning outcomes .

Contents of heuristic learning technology. The essence of heuristic learning is to always try to discover something new. Heuristics comes from the Greek *heuriska*, which means to seek, find, discover.

Heuristics training:

The form of training is heuristic conversation. Questions and answers are organized between teacher and student to understand the essence of the issue and reach consensus.

Teaching method. In the process of creative work, the teacher gives the student focused ideas about the work, guides him in the right direction when his thoughts wander, and organizes a brainstorming session from time to time. This creates a heuristic situation to clarify the issue.

Technological process of this release. This was determined by the student himself. The final result of the implementation of a creative product will depend on the technology chosen by the student. If the chosen path does not work, the teacher will help the student in time. The creative self-realization of the student is the highest issue of heuristic learning. Innovative technologies is almost based on the Socratic method of questioning and reasoning.

In heuristic learning, the situation is the key element of learning. Such the situation activates him from the student's ignorance, his goal leads to the birth of the student's personal ideas, hypotheses, and schemes.

In heuristic learning, the learning outcome cannot be predicted. You may get different answers from each student.

In heuristic learning, the student learns prior knowledge and then applies it to his or her project through live learning. The motto of finding the future by learning from previous knowledge applies here. Heuristic learning is based on the school of free development, and its theory is heuristic didactics.

The subject assigned by the teacher to the student of the English language subject of heuristic educational technology for creative project work: "Forms of singular and plural nouns."

As part of the implementation of heuristic technologies, the process of students' assimilation of educational material has a certain structure and sequence. The teacher creates conditions for difficult situations, offers them to students, then the students are divided into groups.

Small groups come together to share relevant tasks and functions and formulate a problem. Discussions involve small groups that actively use brainstorming, allowing students to come up with hypotheses that cannot be refuted in the early stages of discussion. Activation of student participation in brainstorming is ensured by the absence of criticism from the teacher and students. During the discussion of the problem, students themselves determine the viability of the hypothesis; their logic test is performed. Students draw appropriate conclusions. Thus, there are many solutions to the same problem (multiple hypotheses are put forward during the discussion). Further research allows students to discard unnecessary hypotheses and draw appropriate conclusions. Also, in the process of mastering educational material, students implement projects. They work on the project both individually and in pairs. Projects can also be completed in large groups. Teachers in the classroom organize the space in such a way that students feel comfortable working with each other and discussing various issues. The teacher tries to create an atmosphere of cooperation. The necessary educational materials and support have been generated.

Summary. In conclusion, we can say that the use of pedagogical technologies in teaching philological subjects can be effective in improving learning outcomes. Through the use of technology, students can gain new concepts, practical skills and knowledge, and contextualizing teaching and learning with real-life scenarios allows students to think critically and solve problems, which helps develop problem-solving skills.

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